

1 TITLE

2 **Drivers of municipal solid waste management cost**
3 **based on cost models inherent to sorted and unsorted**
4 **waste**

5 **AUTHORS**

6 Giacomo Di Foggia, Massimo Beccarelli

7 University of Milano-Bicocca, Department of Business and Law

8 Article information

9 *Preprint*

10

11 Di Foggia, G., & Beccarelli, M. (2020). Drivers of municipal solid waste management cost
12 based on cost models inherent to sorted and unsorted waste. *Waste Management, 114*,
13 202–214. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2020.07.012>

14

15 **ABSTRACT**

16 After having divided waste management cost in its cost items, we focus on how well-
17 known exogenous and endogenous drivers impact on such cost items. To this end, we
18 collected empirical data of 6,616 Italian municipalities for a two-year period. We
19 develop four regression-based models to analyze the data according to cost items.
20 Models are also reiterated using different data normalization: cost per ton of waste or
21 waste per capita. Besides exogenous determiners of cost, such as altitude, population
22 density, and coastal zone, results refer to both unsorted and sorted waste management
23 cost items. In this respect economies of scale are confirmed along with the critical role
24 of adequate waste facilities that play a remarkable role in cost minimization.

25 Policymakers and regulators may benefit from such results when it comes to define
26 allowed revenues and design the scope of municipal solid waste regulation.

27 **KEYWORDS:** Municipal solid waste, waste management, sorted and unsorted waste,
28 waste treatment, waste disposal, waste tax

29

30 **1. INTRODUCTION**

31 Scholars have identified a positive and linear relationship between economic growth
32 and waste production, where a 1% increase in the gross domestic product increases
33 the quantity of waste produced by 0.69% (Johnstone and Labonne, 2004). Given that
34 socio-economic trends go hand in hand with environment implications, waste
35 management has also become central to the sustainability policy agenda (Mani and
36 Singh, 2016) and circular economy targets (Zeller et al., 2019) especially in Europe.

37 No wonder that within the waste management industry, what above mentioned clarify
38 the reason municipal solid waste (MSW) has become one of the most important
39 municipal services (Hoornweg and Bhada-Tata, 2012). Therefore, an improvement in
40 the efficiency of this service is recognized as an opportunity for creating jobs,
41 incentivizing responsible consumption, and protecting the environment (Beccarello
42 and Di Foggia, 2018). Given that fees paid by various taxpayers and subsidies from
43 local authorities' budget (World Bank, 2018) finance the service, efficient MSW
44 management reduce the effective tax pressure and increase social welfare (Fuss et al.,
45 2018). This aspect indicates the growing concern about its financial sustainability
46 (Debnath and Bose, 2014; Jacobsen et al., 2013; Lombrano, 2009).

47 Previous literature has recurrently investigated drivers of the MSW management cost
48 (MC), however, given that MSW collection and disposal chain encompasses different
49 phases, we believe that an analysis and breakdown of the components of the MSW
50 management cost may provide a better insight into how and why the identified cost
51 drivers affect specifically cost items that make up the total cost.

52 To perform the analyses we conducted a clustered regression-based analysis using
53 different cost items presented in the models as dependent variables. We modeled data

54 obtained from a sample of 6,616 Italian municipalities; data were extrapolated for a
55 two-year period.

56 From the results both general consideration could be drawn especially with regards to
57 the impact of exogenous variables and specific insight obtained from models related to
58 unsorted and sorted waste.

59 For example, in our analysis, some exogenous drivers such as urban density, altitude,
60 waste production or coastal characteristics, are found to be persistent cost drivers.
61 Instead, concerning the cost drivers of unsorted waste, our results show that the impact
62 of MSW treatment facilities, particularly waste-to-energy plants, significantly affect
63 the cost. An increase in the share of the waste sent to waste-to-energy plants tends to
64 decrease the average cost. Although with worse impact on the environment, similar
65 effect emerged considering the relationship between the share of waste sent to landfills
66 and MC. Nevertheless it is recognized that waste sent to landfills shall be minimized.
67 With regard to sorted waste, result confirm, e.g. the positive impact of the percentage
68 of sorted waste on materials treatment and recycling. Similar to unsorted waste, the
69 higher the share of sorted waste sent to the specific treatment facilities, the lower the
70 cost. The latter point is crucial in today' waste management regulation context in many
71 European countries, ad worldwide in general. To this extent previous literature has
72 been analyzed the expected costs of transferring municipalities to solid waste source
73 separation in order to minimize the waste sent to landfills and increasing the efficiency
74 and amount of recycled waste (Lavee and Nardiya, 2013).

75 Our contribution to the existing literature is twofold. We provide information on how
76 previously analyzed and typical waste management cost drivers influence specific cost
77 items hardly considered before. This is an essential information for supporting
78 regulators of solid waste management as per the identification of allowed revenues and

79 the definition regulation scope. This is particularly important for many European
80 country where the waste regulation is being updated in light of circular economy
81 objective. For example, a recent study highlighted that tendency of productivity decline
82 in the urban waste utilities calling for more efforts to design efficient economic
83 regulation (Simões and Marques, 2012a). In addition, our results show that the unit of
84 measure, costs per ton of waste and costs per capita, may lead to different results in
85 the impact of cost drivers on cost.

86 Based on the foregoing findings, our research has the following policy implications.
87 Industrial policymakers may benefit from our results to identify policy instruments
88 aimed at overcoming critical issues such as the social stigma against the establishment
89 of waste treatment facilities, which hinders their allocation, prevents self-sufficiency
90 in waste management, increases costs, and, eventually, leads to negative environment
91 externalities. Our results may provide and regulators with insights useful to design
92 asymmetric regulations as per the definition of allowed revenues in each of the cost
93 items analyzed in this paper. Local administrators may take advantage of these results
94 for benchmarking purposes, e.g. to better understand the structure of the cost they pay
95 to companies in both phased of the waste treatment chain: collection and disposal.

96 The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 provides a literature
97 review of related research. Section 3 presents the research design, the information
98 pertaining to the sample, the variables generated for analyses, the cost definition
99 relevant to this research, and the models used. Section 4 provides the results of the
100 analyses. These results are discussed in Section 5, which is followed by conclusion in
101 Section 6.

102 **2. LITERATURE**

103 In the study of MSWM efficiency, the identification and significance of cost drivers
104 have been well-documented and they arguably represent some of the most thought-
105 provoking current topics in light of the ongoing debate on optimal cost definition
106 (Kinnaman, 2009). The number of relevant studies on MSW cost has increased (Bohm
107 et al., 2010; Da Cruz et al., 2014; Gullì and Zazzi, 2011; Pérez-López et al., 2016; Sarra
108 et al., 2017), despite the complexity anticipated from scattered and limited data
109 (Tsilemou and Panagiotakopoulos, 2006). These studies have also been prompted by
110 legislations on waste management (Buclet and Godard, 2001); they emerged in Europe
111 and started to grow after the introduction of the 1994 European Directive on packaging
112 waste. On the one hand, the economic literature has been primarily concerned with
113 demand-side issues and the associated policy implications (Goddard, 1995); on the
114 other hand, scholars have analyzed multiple output cost structures for waste
115 management (Callan and Thomas, 2001). For example, research has concentrated on
116 costs related to separate waste and recycling; scholars have also proposed tools to
117 calculate the full collection costs of different types of waste (D'Onza et al., 2016) or
118 econometric models to predict where the potential for economically efficient recycling
119 is the highest (Lavee and Khatib, 2010). Moreover, literature has investigated the
120 economic efficiency of MSW collection companies for verifying the drivers for
121 efficiency, finding that these drivers differ for different types of waste (UNEP, 2012).
122 Different approaches have been proposed in an effort to shed some light on this issue.
123 For example, previous literature has summarized the results of studies examining
124 different cost drivers of waste management: market structure where a consensus
125 regarding the economies of scale, scope and density was identified, ownership where
126 the period of analysis was identified as an important variable, incentives where
127 differently from economies of scale the paper found low agreement in their effect of

128 performance, and benchmarking. (Simões and Marques, 2012b). In fact, besides public
129 firms, private operators have emerged to run the service given the rising pressure in
130 terms of cost efficiency that has pushed governments to transfer a part of waste
131 services to the private companies (Jacobsen et al., 2013). This has given rise to an
132 important question related to market provision—whether profit-seeking firms will
133 generate socially acceptable outcomes (Kinnaman, 2009). In this context, the open-
134 ended debate on productivity enhancements in public versus private service
135 production has yielded mixed results (Bel and Fageda, 2010; Simões et al., 2012). In
136 this regard, empirical evidence based on the MSWM business model shows that
137 economic and political factors exert varied impacts on the MSWM of private and public
138 companies (Plata-Díaz et al., 2014).

139 Apart from this, it can be argued that firm dimension, inter-firm relationships,
140 alternative technologies, and landfill capacity also exert significant impacts
141 (Lombrano, 2009), similar to the economies of scale and scope. Based on the
142 population of municipalities, some evidence about the economies of scale indicate that
143 private MSWM operators do not outperform the public entities (Bel and Fageda, 2010).
144 The aforementioned works have made considerable progress in explaining the
145 statistically significant drivers of MSW cost by using robust approaches and providing
146 information from different geographies. While the quantity of waste generated has
147 been one of the most widely investigated drivers, , the important waste management
148 methods, such as curbside or street bin (Guerrini et al., 2017) or door-to-door service,
149 have received limited attention; these methods are crucial as they exert a significant
150 impact on work organization in light of the fact that many factors may play a role
151 regardless of the assessment methods (Allesch and Brunner, 2014) and that both

152 controllable and non-controllable factors can significantly impact the cost (De Jaeger
153 and Rogge, 2013).

154 The methods employed to perform the service and the population size and density also
155 impact the cost because of the economies of scale (De Jaeger et al., 2011). In fact, the
156 percentage of sorted waste has been found to exert varied impacts on the cost (Chifari
157 et al., 2017; Greco et al., 2015) since sorted waste can both positively and negatively
158 impact the cost by increasing collection and processing efficiency. In this regards an
159 empirical simulation indicated that by adopting recycling, municipalities would be able
160 to reduce waste management direct costs by 11% (Lavee, 2007). It has traditionally
161 been argued that recycling municipal solid waste (MSW) is usually not economically
162 viable Morphological and geographical drivers, such as surface and altitude and
163 latitude of territories (Passarini et al., 2011), and socioeconomic drivers, such as
164 available income (Mazzanti et al., 2008), political orientation of the governing party at
165 municipal levels and above (Benito-López et al., 2011), and environmental targets
166 (Beccarello and Di Foggia, 2016), have also been investigated. Production technologies
167 (Swart and Groot, 2015; Tisserant et al., 2017) and the use of waste management
168 facilities (Chu et al., 2019; Tsilemou and Panagiotakopoulos, 2006) have also been
169 identified as worth noting. Some studies have approximated cost functions,
170 highlighting the evolution of and the differences in organizational, financial,
171 management, and technological schemes (Bohm et al., 2010); another study analyzing
172 cost functions has proposed an approach to select different MSW strategies according
173 to the waste recovery technology and the utility functional specification (Swart and
174 Groot, 2015).

175 Having said that, although the number of studies has increased over the past, most of
176 the mentioned studies have focused on the drivers of MSWM cost. However, this study

177 contributes to the literature by breaking down its various components. The study
178 discusses the cost items incurred during different phases of the service, from waste
179 collection to waste disposal.

180 **3. RESEARCH DESIGN**

181 In order to evaluate how and to what extent some MSW-related cost drivers influence
182 specific cost items that add to the MC we conducted a clustered regression analysis
183 based on a two-year period. We developed two models inherent to unsorted and sorted
184 waste cost items: each model is formalized using both costs per ton of waste, and costs
185 per capita.

186 **3.1. Population and sample**

187 According to ISTAT, 60.432 million people lived in 7,978 municipalities in 2018. Our
188 sample contained 6,616 municipalities, that is, 82.9% of all the Italian municipalities,
189 covering 91.5% of the population. The variables were generated by querying official
190 data published by the Public finance department of the Internal Minister, the Italian
191 National Institute for Environmental Protection and Research (ISPRA), and the Italian
192 National Institute for Statistics (ISTAT) based on economic, waste, and territorial data,
193 respectively. We collected the data for a two-years period; specifically 2017 and 2018.
194 The economic variables were constructed using official information, such as waste tax
195 revenues, indicated in the environmental declaration model (MUD), which is updated
196 annually by municipalities, their consortia, or delegated entities. The computation of
197 costs per ton of waste is based on the data published by ISPRA, while the demographic
198 and morphological data were extrapolated from ISTAT.

199 **3.2. Variables and labels**

200 Our variable can be classified labelled as exogenous e.g. morphological variables, cost-
201 related and endogenous e.g. plants and waste. We identified the following exogenous
202 drivers to perform our analyses: *alt*: meters above sea level, *axr*: km² per km of road,
203 *coast*: coastal municipality, *density*: people or waste per square kilometer, *scale*: scale
204 of service. Endogenous drivers were: *adig*: the share of waste sent to anaerobic
205 digestion plants, *wet*: the share of wet fraction in sorted waste, *compo*: the share of
206 waste sent to composting plants in total waste, *glass*: the share of glass in sorted waste,
207 *integ*: the share of waste sent to integrated treatment plants, *landfill*: the share of waste
208 to landfill in total waste, *mbt*: the share of waste sent to mechanical biological
209 treatment plants, *metal*: the share of metal, *rev*: municipal revenues, *kg*: per capita
210 waste produced, *paper*: the share of paper, *plastic*: the share of plastic, *perso*: the
211 percentage of sorted waste, *wte*: the share of waste sent to incinerator and waste-to-
212 energy plants.

213 Considering the cost items-related variables we identified: *ctc*: collection and transport
214 cost, *MC*: municipal solid waste management cost, *msc*: material sorted waste cost,
215 *ouc*: other unsorted waste cost, *SOMC*: sorted waste management cost, *swc*: the street
216 sweeping and washing cost, *tdc*: the treatment and disposal cost, *trc*: the treatment
217 and recycling cost, net of material and energy sales, *UNMC*: unsorted waste
218 management cost.

219 As previously introduced, the aforementioned variables were normalized according to
220 the unit of measure: costs per ton of waste and costs per capita. Table 1 presents
221 descriptive statistics.

222 Table 1: descriptive statistics

Variable	Measure	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
alt	log	13,152	5.305	1.315	0.000	7.618
axr	km2	12,646	0.715	1.090	0.011	23.343
coast	dummy	13,156	0.073	0.260	0.000	1.000
scale	log	12,646	21.904	4.127	9.496	45.330
ctc	per capita	12,788	27.239	26.329	1.140	433.630
den	per capita	13,156	4.810	1.422	-0.266	9.380
msc	per capita	12,758	37.431	26.134	1.020	598.680
kg	per capita	13,139	450.632	152.694	121.240	1494.640
MC	per capita	13,232	144.094	65.635	19.040	1186.300
rev	per capita	12,910	7.286	0.603	5.998	11.295
SOMC	per capita	13,129	47.877	31.184	2.730	620.610
swc	per capita	10,716	16.217	17.977	1.400	319.980
tdc	per capita	12,627	25.499	17.761	1.030	199.890
trc	per capita	10,649	13.570	10.298	1.830	180.580
UNMC	per capita	13,102	54.916	37.535	9.380	582.270
adig	percent	13,232	2.600	3.770	0.000	23.444
bio	percent	11,799	37.777	14.472	0.007	100.000
compo	percent	13,232	14.221	7.148	0.000	34.971
glass	percent	12,537	16.145	8.931	0.005	63.726
integ	percent	13,232	10.644	12.445	0.000	55.531
land	percent	12,966	22.523	20.860	3.316	92.767
mbt	percent	13,232	29.677	20.797	0.000	86.199
metal	percent	11,754	2.780	2.769	0.000	53.991
paper	percent	12,629	18.587	7.605	0.115	69.968
plastic	percent	12,584	9.651	5.831	0.005	75.000
perso	percent	13,174	59.696	20.655	0.002	98.193
textile	percent	9,464	1.266	1.178	0.003	10.364
weee	percent	11,449	2.040	1.523	0.000	20.343
wte	percent	13,232	21.798	15.398	0.000	73.527
ctc	per ton	12,789	172.534	149.692	10.100	1342.000
den	per ton	13,098	3.970	1.472	-0.853	8.458
msc	per ton	12,649	161.334	138.931	10.000	2794.000
MC	per ton	13,232	331.683	117.026	65.800	1002.400
rev	per ton	12,910	8.127	0.660	6.657	11.759
SOMC	per ton	13,011	195.520	143.217	5.900	1213.300
swc	per ton	9,594	40.891	38.032	10.000	413.900
tdc	per ton	12,649	152.547	72.679	10.400	1133.900
trc	per ton	10,721	56.503	97.034	10.000	4866.900
UNMC	per ton	13,100	343.099	191.268	1.600	2214.500

223 Source: Own elaboration.

224 **3.3. Cost definition**

225 The identification of drivers of MC must consider the different cost items making up
226 the cost as equation 1 formalizes.

(1)
$$MC = UNMC + SOMC + AC + CK$$

227 In which UNMC can also be decomposed as in equation 2.

(2)
$$UNMC = ctc + swc + tdc + CC_{unsorted}$$

228 Similarly SOMC can be decomposed as equation 3.

(3)
$$SOMC = msc + trc + CC_{sorted}$$

229 For the purposes of our analyses common costs and capital costs were excluded
230 because of two reasons: first they could not be allocated to UNMC or SOMR
231 respectively, marginal amounts, on average less than 4% of MC.

232 Figure 1 describes the phases in which the cost under examination in this paper occur.
233 This is particularly important since the costs that the regulation should consider are
234 those related to all the activities aimed at optimizing waste management, i.e. collection,
235 transport, treatment, recovery and disposal of waste, including the control of these
236 operations, sweeping and street cleaning, and the management of fees and user
237 relations (Di Foggia and Beccarello, 2020).

238 Figure 1: Typologies of municipal solid waste management cost

239

240

Source: own elaboration

241 Although the MSWM cost can be divided into unsorted and sorted waste management,
 242 it must be noted that several indivisible common costs are incurred for managing both
 243 types of waste; these costs are embedded in the analysis. Specifically, common costs
 244 could be included in the unsorted and sorted costs or embedded as independent
 245 variable within the models considered in this study. Figure 2 contains information
 246 regarding the average cost per typology of cost and per unit of measure, such figures
 247 stem from the breakdown of the MSWM cost.

248 Figure 2: Average cost per cost items

249 Source: own elaboration based on ISPRA. Common costs excluded as not allocated to
 250 waste typologies.

251 3.4. The model

252 This study hypothesizes that different cost drivers influence the components of the
 253 MSWM cost with different intensity. In order to ascertain the relationship and the
 254 influence of drivers on waste management costs, it is appropriate to perform an
 255 econometric analysis using regression models. Hence, we analyzed the data using
 256 separate models according to the typologies of costs and the units of measure, that is,
 257 per ton of waste or per capita waste. We performed a clustered regression that given
 258 the two-years period and the number of observations outperformed conventional
 259 cross-section regression, which could missed the specific effects of each municipality
 260 and potential changes overtime. In such a way the standard errors allowed for
 261 intragroup correlation. Properties of the following model justify its implementation.
 262 Equation 4 formalizes the model related to unsorted waste

$$(4) \quad COST = \alpha + \beta_1 axr + \beta_2 coast + \beta_3 alt + \beta_4 perso + \beta_5 kg + \beta_6 rev + \beta_7 density + \beta_8 scale + PLANTS + \varepsilon$$

263 In equation 4 the dependent variable *COST* resamples the following cost items: *swc*,
 264 *ctc*, *tfc*, *UNMC*, *MC*. Independent variables follow together with the set of independent
 265 variables embracing the share of waste sent to waste treatment facilities as in equation
 266 5.

$$(5) \quad PLANTS = \beta_9 wte + \beta_{10} landfill + \beta_{11} mbt$$

267 Similarly, Equation 6 formalizes the model related to unsorted waste:

$$(6) \quad COST = \alpha + \beta_1 axr + \beta_2 coast + \beta_3 alt + \beta_4 perso + \beta_5 kg + \beta_6 rev + \beta_7 density + \beta_8 scale + PLANTS + MATERIALS + \varepsilon$$

268 In equation 6 the dependent variable *COST* resamples the following cost items: *msc*,
 269 *trc*, *SOMC*, *MC*. Again, independent variable follow where the set of independent
 270 variables embracing the share of waste sent to waste treatment facilities are
 271 summarized in equation 7.

$$(7) \quad PLANTS = \beta_9 mbt + \beta_{10} integ + \beta_{11} compo + \beta_{12} adig$$

272 In addition, the set of independent variables representing the share of materials types
 273 MATERIALS is formalized in equation 7.

$$(8) \quad MATERIALS = \beta_{13} plastic + \beta_{14} paper + \beta_{15} metal + \beta_{16} glass + \beta_{17} bio$$

274 Annex 1 presents a correlation matrix of all the variables used in the models inherent
 275 to unsorted waste while annex 2 presents a correlation matrix of all the variables used
 276 in the models inherent to sorted waste.

277 **4. RESULTS**

278 Consistently with research design our results are presented both in costs per ton of
 279 waste, i.e. table 2 and table 3, see annex 3 for variance inflation factors (VIFs), and costs
 280 per capita as in table 4 and table 5, see annex 4 for VIFs. Additionally, table 6 presents a
 281 synthesis of prominent evidences emerged from a cross reading of the tables.

282 **4.1.Per ton of MSW**

283 By considering table 2, and specifically the column that refers to UNMC, it is possible
 284 to infer that municipalities with higher density tend to show lower unsorted waste
 285 management costs. On the contrary, there is a significant increase in cost due to the
 286 coastal character of the municipality. The percent of sorted waste seems is associated
 287 with a tiny increase in cost, probably because of scale economies the impact on SOMC.
 288 As far as waste treatment and disposal facilities' equipment are concerned, there is a
 289 noticeable impact on UNMC reduction correlated with the use of waste management
 290 facilities: waste-to-energy plants and landfills. The same cannot be said for
 291 mechanical-biological treatment despite their recognized role in achieving circular
 292 economy objectives.

293 Table 2: Regression analysis of unsorted waste as in Equation 4 – cost per ton of waste

VARIABLES	(1) ut1 swc	(2) ut2 ctc	(3) ut3 tdc	(4) ut4 UNMC	(5) ut5 MC
axr	0.00850 (0.00609)	-0.0167*** (0.00579)	-0.0177*** (0.00466)	-0.0114*** (0.00402)	-0.000584 (0.000405)
coast	0.343*** (0.0333)	0.174*** (0.0363)	0.0569*** (0.0181)	0.146*** (0.0233)	0.0274*** (0.00235)
alt	0.0343*** (0.00583)	-0.0156*** (0.00603)	-0.0263*** (0.00332)	-0.0232*** (0.00395)	-0.000580 (0.000437)
perso	-0.00192*** (0.000435)	0.00949*** (0.000405)	0.00393*** (0.000244)	0.00790*** (0.000284)	1.18e-06 (2.87e-05)
kg	-0.0508* (0.0269)	-0.165*** (0.0255)	-0.0527*** (0.0154)	-0.109*** (0.0171)	-0.0198*** (0.00196)
rev	0.258***	0.133***	0.0516***	0.0887***	0.0252***

	(0.0164)	(0.0148)	(0.00884)	(0.00988)	(0.00104)
den	0.0546***	-0.0567***	-0.0363***	-0.0467***	-0.00103**
	(0.00724)	(0.00679)	(0.00380)	(0.00445)	(0.000455)
scale	0.00109	-0.0285***	-0.000121	-0.0128***	9.66e-05
	(0.00194)	(0.00182)	(0.00111)	(0.00131)	(0.000133)
wte	0.000275	-0.000191	-0.00183***	-0.00102***	-0.000451***
	(0.000517)	(0.000473)	(0.000322)	(0.000363)	(3.42e-05)
land	-0.00400***	-0.00303***	-0.00345***	-0.00345***	-0.000501***
	(0.000520)	(0.000494)	(0.000301)	(0.000346)	(3.16e-05)
mbt	0.00746***	0.00557***	0.00392***	0.00417***	0.00108***
	(0.000485)	(0.000504)	(0.000307)	(0.000360)	(3.33e-05)
Constant	1.177***	5.063***	4.896***	5.742***	1.654***
	(0.244)	(0.230)	(0.138)	(0.155)	(0.0172)
Observations	8,976	11,984	11,800	12,230	12,350
R-squared	0.156	0.142	0.083	0.154	0.344

Standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

294
295
296

Source: own elaboration

297 The results concerning the drivers of SOMC report similarities in the information
298 pertaining to the analysis of undifferentiated collection. A coastal municipality is
299 associated with an increase in cost and a higher altitude corresponds to a lower cost
300 even if the percentage of sorted collection is negatively correlated with the altitude.
301 The waste production density, i.e. waste produced per square kilometer, contributes
302 significantly to cost reduction as expected. Result also confirms the role of the use of
303 waste management facilities as a significant cost reduction driver, with the exception
304 of mechanical biological treatment. Concerning the characteristic of the service, a
305 prominent factor is the percentage of separate waste collection. There are no
306 noteworthy results regarding the percentage of different materials that make up the
307 sorted waste, with the exception of glass, wet faction and paper.

308 Table 3: Regression analysis of sorted waste, as in Equation 6 – cost per ton of waste

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
VARIABLES	st1	st2	st3	st4
	msc	trc	SOMC	MC
axr	0.0167**	0.00930	0.0273***	-6.25e-05

	(0.00695)	(0.00691)	(0.00616)	(0.000505)
coast	0.0860**	0.0857**	0.0872**	0.0164***
	(0.0376)	(0.0359)	(0.0359)	(0.00225)
alt	-0.0208***	-0.00811	-0.0178***	-0.00444***
	(0.00664)	(0.00594)	(0.00631)	(0.000456)
perso	-0.00374***	-0.00101*	-0.00229***	0.000159***
	(0.000588)	(0.000543)	(0.000580)	(3.86e-05)
kg	-0.271***	-0.122***	-0.223***	-0.0185***
	(0.0310)	(0.0273)	(0.0310)	(0.00214)
rev	0.111***	0.183***	0.167***	0.0222***
	(0.0171)	(0.0150)	(0.0167)	(0.00119)
den	-0.0146**	0.0272***	-6.79e-05	-0.00104**
	(0.00738)	(0.00638)	(0.00658)	(0.000459)
scale	0.0115***	4.31e-05	0.0155***	0.000630***
	(0.00217)	(0.00194)	(0.00207)	(0.000141)
plastic	0.0161***	0.00205	0.0139***	0.000204*
	(0.00170)	(0.00149)	(0.00161)	(0.000115)
paper	0.00215	-0.0110***	-0.00416***	-0.000620***
	(0.00144)	(0.00133)	(0.00146)	(9.85e-05)
metal	-0.0103**	-0.00689*	-0.0187***	0.000279
	(0.00416)	(0.00379)	(0.00423)	(0.000224)
glass	0.00489***	0.00124	0.000789	0.000627***
	(0.00162)	(0.00145)	(0.00162)	(9.68e-05)
wet	0.00759***	0.000453	0.00706***	-0.000107*
	(0.000964)	(0.000825)	(0.000925)	(5.91e-05)
mbt	0.00850***	0.00704***	0.00577***	0.000930***
	(0.000582)	(0.000556)	(0.000553)	(3.73e-05)
integ	0.00300***	-0.00746***	0.00123***	-0.000520***
	(0.000513)	(0.000498)	(0.000474)	(3.95e-05)
adig	-0.00456*	0.0153***	-0.000776	-0.00210***
	(0.00252)	(0.00264)	(0.00281)	(0.000157)
compo	-2.12e-05	-0.00954***	0.00164	-0.000655***
	(0.00121)	(0.00101)	(0.00107)	(7.28e-05)
Constant	4.861***	3.150***	4.395***	1.677***
	(0.295)	(0.259)	(0.293)	(0.0204)
Observations	10,045	8,801	10,323	10,451
R-squared	0.172	0.199	0.141	0.404

309 Standard errors in parentheses
310 *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

311 Source: own elaboration

312 4.2. Per capita

313 Similar to the per ton analysis, the cost determinants can be analyzed reading the
314 column that refer to UNMC of table 4. Considering exogenous drivers, it can be seen
315 that the density plays an important role and also in this case, the cost reduction

316 resulting from altitude is also significant as it is the fact of being a coastal municipality
317 that is associated with higher cost. Concerning the use of waste management facilities,
318 there is a noticeable impact of waste-to-energy plants and landfills in the territory on
319 cost reduction. An assessment of some of the characteristics of the service shows that
320 the waste produced per capita is significant and increases the cost, while the percentage
321 of sorted waste decreases the cost. Similar to the earlier case, economies of scale are
322 also noted in this version.

323 Table 4: Regression analysis of unsorted waste, as in Equation 4 – cost per capita

VARIABLES	(1) up1 swc	(2) up2 ctc	(3) up3 tdc	(4) up4 UNMC	(5) up5 MC
axr	0.00242 (0.00830)	-0.0166*** (0.00644)	-0.0169*** (0.00618)	-0.0138*** (0.00485)	-0.00555* (0.00317)
coast	0.419*** (0.0395)	0.296*** (0.0365)	0.176*** (0.0209)	0.252*** (0.0228)	0.230*** (0.0145)
alt	0.0426*** (0.00755)	0.0101* (0.00592)	-2.35e-05 (0.00376)	0.00224 (0.00378)	-0.00552** (0.00257)
perso	-0.00208*** (0.000520)	-0.0106*** (0.000410)	-0.0168*** (0.000295)	-0.0127*** (0.000271)	-0.000198 (0.000167)
kg	0.442*** (0.0338)	0.360*** (0.0250)	0.622*** (0.0193)	0.470*** (0.0179)	0.497*** (0.0131)
rev	0.315*** (0.0190)	0.133*** (0.0151)	0.0403*** (0.0106)	0.0888*** (0.0101)	0.125*** (0.00680)
den	0.0782*** (0.00876)	-0.0406*** (0.00684)	-0.0271*** (0.00464)	-0.0312*** (0.00451)	-0.00340 (0.00283)
scale	0.00920*** (0.00240)	-0.0306*** (0.00184)	-0.00158 (0.00130)	-0.0134*** (0.00123)	0.000568 (0.000812)
wte	-0.000964 (0.000607)	-0.00184*** (0.000477)	-0.00349*** (0.000378)	-0.00256*** (0.000318)	-0.00272*** (0.000199)
land	-0.00358*** (0.000607)	-0.00241*** (0.000502)	-0.00276*** (0.000374)	-0.00288*** (0.000331)	-0.00228*** (0.000196)
mbt	0.00794*** (0.000590)	0.00509*** (0.000511)	0.00296*** (0.000380)	0.00370*** (0.000349)	0.00479*** (0.000210)
Constant	-3.428*** (0.250)	1.215*** (0.188)	0.193 (0.142)	1.522*** (0.135)	0.974*** (0.0989)
Observations	10,043	11,979	11,779	12,229	12,350
R-squared	0.152	0.243	0.471	0.402	0.367

324

325 Standard errors in parentheses
 326 *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1
 327 Source: own elaboration

328 Results concerning the determinants of the cost of sorted waste per capita report
 329 similarities in information pertaining to the analysis of undifferentiated collection.
 330 Population density contributes significantly to cost reduction even if its effect is found
 331 to be controversial (Di Foggia and Beccarello, 2018; Dijkgraaf and Gradus, 2015).
 332 Similar to the previous case, the use of waste management facilities within the territory
 333 is a significant cost reduction driver, with the exception of mechanical biological
 334 treatment. Concerning the characteristic of the service, the most important factor is
 335 the production of waste per capita that concur to a higher cost. Concerning the
 336 percentage of different materials that make up separate waste collection, the only
 337 significant materials are glass, wet fraction and paper.

338 Table 5: Regression analysis of sorted waste, as in Equation 6 – cost per capita

VARIABLES	(1) sp1 msc	(2) sp2 trc	(3) sp3 SOMC	(4) sp4 MC
axr	0.0155** (0.00700)	0.0157** (0.00737)	0.0197*** (0.00612)	-0.00349 (0.00357)
coast	0.159*** (0.0400)	0.0749** (0.0374)	0.134*** (0.0346)	0.156*** (0.0140)
alt	-0.0158** (0.00714)	-0.00578 (0.00673)	-0.0174*** (0.00608)	-0.0305*** (0.00265)
perso	0.0113*** (0.000623)	0.0123*** (0.000530)	0.0120*** (0.000563)	0.000491** (0.000225)
kg	0.384*** (0.0323)	0.500*** (0.0285)	0.385*** (0.0308)	0.517*** (0.0153)
rev	0.106*** (0.0179)	0.132*** (0.0155)	0.148*** (0.0162)	0.104*** (0.00737)
den	-0.0185** (0.00781)	0.0385*** (0.00660)	-0.00479 (0.00635)	-0.00641** (0.00278)
scale	0.0128*** (0.00222)	0.00327 (0.00204)	0.0130*** (0.00202)	0.00309*** (0.000839)
plastic	0.0204*** (0.00176)	0.00621*** (0.00149)	0.0133*** (0.00155)	0.000684 (0.000715)
paper	0.00157	-0.0126***	-0.00468***	-0.00290***

	(0.00150)	(0.00132)	(0.00135)	(0.000553)
metal	-0.0144***	-0.0184***	-0.0239***	5.97e-05
	(0.00402)	(0.00362)	(0.00408)	(0.00146)
glass	0.00410**	0.00387***	-0.000212	0.00273***
	(0.00166)	(0.00143)	(0.00157)	(0.000641)
wet	0.00774***	-0.000382	0.00658***	-0.00108***
	(0.000984)	(0.000839)	(0.000871)	(0.000354)
mbt	0.00591***	0.00542***	0.00407***	0.00460***
	(0.000610)	(0.000570)	(0.000526)	(0.000215)
integ	0.00319***	-0.00705***	0.000623	-0.00367***
	(0.000557)	(0.000529)	(0.000466)	(0.000224)
adig	-0.00777***	0.00764***	-0.00138	-0.0111***
	(0.00283)	(0.00296)	(0.00262)	(0.000891)
compo	-0.000641	-0.0104***	-7.30e-06	-0.00370***
	(0.00126)	(0.00105)	(0.00104)	(0.000420)
Constant	-1.246***	-2.392***	-1.033***	1.117***
	(0.275)	(0.237)	(0.257)	(0.125)
Observations	10,114	8,813	10,371	10,451
R-squared	0.126	0.179	0.173	0.443

Standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

339
340
341

Source: own elaboration

342 To conclude this section, table 6 presents prominent cost drivers that according to our
343 models deserve special attention being them used in both models and resulted
344 significant in influencing specific cost items under investigation in this paper.

345 Table 6: focus of cost drivers for unsorted and sorted waste cost items

variable	Impact	ctc	tdc	msc	trc
axr	Less urbanized municipalities are associated with lower costs taking into account the cost items of the unsorted waste; the same cannot be said for the cost items related to the sorted waste. This is partially explained by increased sorting and management costs of the sorted fraction where waste production is dispersed; e.g. increased mileage to optimize vehicle loading and deliver waste to recovery and recycling plants.	-	-	+	(+)
alt	At mountain and hill municipalities corresponds a lower waste management cost. This is do to the morphological characteristics of Italy with plenty of hillside villages with no o a few economic activities.	-	-	-	-
coast	Coastal municipalities have higher costs in all cost items considered. This paper does not go into the subject in depth but a potential explanation is related to tourism flows.	+	+	+	+
perso	The impact of the separate collection rate is ambiguous as the literature suggests. There are economies of scale for both cost	+	+	-	-

	items related to the sorted waste. The opposite is true for the items related to the unsorted waste.				
kg	As waste per capita increases, the cost of management decreases. Although circular economy objectives require waste generation to be reduced, it is clear that the cost of management decreases as waste generation per capita increases, other things being equal. One possible explanation, for example, is the optimization of collection for the same number of kilometers travelled.	-	-	-	-
rev	There is a correlation between the cost of waste management and the municipality' revenues. Municipalities with higher budget per waste produced have a higher percentage of manufacturing and tertiary activities. The type of waste produced increases and some of it is assimilated to municipal waste.	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)
den	The production of waste per kilometre is correlated to the reduction in the cost of management of the unsorted waste while for the sorted waste there is a reduction in the cost of sorting and management of materials.	-	-	-	(+)
scale	Economies of scale related to the size of the service are especially noticeable in the management of the unsorted waste. This is also due to the presence of treatment and disposal plants.	-	(-)	(+)	(+)
mbt	Mechanical biological treatment plants, although useful for achieving circular economy objectives, tend to increase costs.	+	+	+	+
Landfill	Despite negative externalities this solution generates it is still widely used because of its low cost.	-	-		
wte	Incinerator with energy recovery play a remarkable role in reducing cost.	-	-	NA	NA
adig	Cost reduction observed in material sorting cost items; the opposite as long as treatment and recycling is concerned.	NA	NA	-	+
compo	Cost reduction observed in both cost items but significant only as long as treatment and recycling is concerned.	NA	NA	(-)	-
integ	Cost reduction observed regarding treatment and recycling. the opposite as long as material sorting and collection is concerned.	NA	NA	+	-

346 Source elaboration. Non-significant values in parentheses.

347 5. DISCUSSION

348 The results of the analysis of our models show that the impact of determinants varies
349 according to the sub-cost items and the units of measure—cost per capita and cost per
350 ton. We go one step further by cross-referencing the results concerning the cost drivers
351 of unsorted waste and using the total cost as a comparison variable. As a result of this
352 cross-referencing, we confirm significant relationships in the case of the variables used,
353 regardless of the unit of analysis, per capita or per ton. Specifically, we believe that it
354 is useful to underline some aspects not considered in the literature.

355 We begin our considerations by emphasizing the role of the use of waste management
356 facilities; waste-to-energy plants and landfills play a remarkable role (Liu et al., 2019;
357 Makarichi et al., 2018; Swart and Groot, 2015) in cost determination, highlighting the
358 significance of making self-sufficiency in waste management capacity a common policy
359 objective. Although our results show that both waste disposal options lower the
360 MSWM cost, the significance of waste-to-energy parts is widely recognized in the
361 context of a circular economy (Malinauskaite et al., 2017). Concerning modern waste
362 legislation, it aims to reduce landfill through regulations, landfill tax, and landfill bans
363 (Scharff, 2014). In this regard, estimates show that Italy alone would require an
364 additional treatment capacity of 6.3 million tons per year of waste-to-energy plants. In
365 order to solve the dilemma of energy demand, waste management, and greenhouse gas
366 emission simultaneously and to achieve a circular industrial economy, it would be
367 viable to establish waste-to-energy supply chains (Pan et al., 2015). Similarly, the
368 selection of different waste management strategies based on waste recovery
369 technologies and the utility functional specification (Swart and Groot, 2015) would be
370 crucial. This is because, among the waste treatment technologies, certain
371 technologies, such as the mechanical biological treatment, do not act in the same way
372 as that of waste-to-energy plants. It has been found that mechanical biological
373 treatment facilities contribute to cost increase. Therefore, it is accepted that, in many
374 types of facilities, an increase in capacity lowers costs.

375 The role of the economies of scale in reducing the cost of MSWM has also been
376 confirmed—an increase in the size of the service leads to a reduction in costs (Bel and
377 Fageda, 2010; Callan and Thomas, 2001). Although circular economy targets require
378 upgradation of the endowment of waste treatment facilities, the realization of
379 economies of scale through the development of new waste management facilities is

380 subject to legislative factors, such as prescriptive or enabling legislation; international,
381 national, regional, and municipal legislations, and technical legislation.

382 Our results also indicate that a higher degree of density corresponds to a lower cost of
383 service (Bartolacci et al., 2019; Greco et al., 2015; Mani and Singh, 2016) that fosters
384 MSWM operations. This result gains importance in light of recent World Bank
385 forecasts as per which the annual waste generation is projected to increase by 70% from
386 2016 levels (which accounted for 2.01 billion tons of MSW generated globally in cities)
387 to 3.40 billion tons in 2050. The results also indicate that coastal municipalities incur
388 higher cost. This may attributed to tourist activities (Arbulú et al., 2015; Greco et al.,
389 2018); however, limited attention has been paid to how and to what extent tourism
390 increases the costs of solid waste collection (Greco et al., 2018). It has also been noted
391 that the cost of service is related with the municipality' budget.

392 Deductions, as the ones outlined above, can be drawn for sorted waste. From our
393 analyses, the impact of separate collection, and in turn of the recycling targets, on cost
394 is not unambiguous. In fact, it depends on many factors including, as the Italian system
395 is set up, the revenues from the sale of materials obtained from separate collection
396 (there is also an agreement between municipalities and the national packaging
397 consortium). Since these prices in recent years have shown fluctuating trends its
398 impact is not easily measurable through an econometric model that includes a two-
399 year period. Among the various materials that make up separate waste, the percentage
400 of glass tends to increase costs, while paper reduces costs. In the case of paper, the
401 lower prices may be attributed to a significant reduction in pulping prices consequent
402 to new international customs barriers on imports. For glass, the increase in prices can
403 be attributed to the surprising increase in the collection rates and the disbursements
404 made alongside the simultaneous fall in the auction value of scrap due to the saturation

405 of treatment plants. For plastic, in southern regions, a significant increase in the
406 amount of packaging waste due to its poor quality has generated additional costs for
407 material sorting and waste management.

408 The use of waste management facilities for the treatment of sorted waste contributes
409 to cost reduction, with the exception of mechanical biological treatment. In this case,
410 therefore, plant capacity plays a fundamental role in achieving the objectives of circular
411 economy. Consistent with findings related to unsorted waste, the study confirms the
412 role of the economies of scale in the total cost. Since our findings are based on Italian
413 municipalities, the results from such analyses should be treated with caution,
414 especially for comparative purposes. For example, one potential concern about our
415 findings is the possibility of alternative scope of cost items. However, our results are
416 reliable, given the internal validity and the consistency of our findings with those in
417 mainstream literature, especially regarding the role of the economies of scale and other
418 widely considered cost drivers.

419 **6. CONCLUSION**

420 We have given an account of how cost drivers impact on waste management cost
421 according to different cost items. After having divided waste management cost in its
422 cost items we have focuses on how exogenous and endogenous drivers impact on such
423 cost items. We have performed four regression-based models to analyze the data
424 according to cost items. Models have also been reiterated using different data
425 normalization: cost per ton of waste or waste per capita. Besides exogenous
426 determiners of cost, such as altitude, population density, and coastal zone, results refer
427 to both unsorted and sorted waste management cost items. In this respect economies
428 of scale are confirmed along with the critical role of adequate waste facilities that play
429 a remarkable role in cost minimization.

430 Results have also confirmed that they differ according to the unit of the selected
431 measures. From the results we can also draw two conclusions for unsorted and sorted
432 waste, respectively.

433 As regards cost drivers of unsorted waste, consistently with previous literature our
434 results confirm the role of the economies of scale, the role of density and the role of
435 geographical variables. Our results add to the exiting knowledge the role of being a
436 coastal municipality Results also highlight the impact of the use of treatment or
437 disposal facilities, such as waste-to-energy plants, in the transition towards a circular
438 economy. Similarly, results concerning the cost drivers of sorted waste have suggested
439 that the use of facilities for the treatment of sorted waste reduces costs, with the
440 exception of mechanical biological treatment. Concerning sorted waste materials, a
441 higher percentage of glass contributes toward increasing costs, while a higher share of
442 paper lowers costs. Our research suggests that the policymakers should identify policy
443 measures to overcome critical issues, such as the social stigma against the
444 establishment of waste treatment facilities that hinders their allocation; for example,
445 the policymakers can refer to the European legislation when designing the policy
446 instruments. This would also guarantee consistency between the cost of the service and
447 the level of quality.

448 Besides benefits for industrial policymakers, our results may provide and regulators
449 with insights useful to design asymmetric regulations as per the definition of allowed
450 revenues in each of the cost items and local administrators may take advantage of these
451 results for benchmarking purposes. In order to move toward a circular economy, it
452 would be important to upgrade the endowment of waste treatment facilities; it is widely
453 recognized as a prominent step for realizing the economies of scale.

454

455 REFERENCES

456

- 457 Allesch, A., Brunner, P.H., 2014. Assessment methods for solid waste management: A
 458 literature review. *Waste Manag. Res.* 32, 461–473.
 459 <https://doi.org/10.1177/0734242X14535653>
- 460 Arbulú, I., Lozano, J., Rey-Maqueira, J., 2015. Tourism and solid waste generation in
 461 Europe: A panel data assessment of the Environmental Kuznets Curve. *Waste*
 462 *Manag.* 46, 628–636. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.WASMAN.2015.04.014>
- 463 Bartolacci, F., Del Gobbo, R., Paolini, A., Soverchia, M., 2019. Efficiency in waste
 464 management companies: A proposal to assess scale economies. *Resour. Conserv.*
 465 *Recycl.* 148, 124–131. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.RESCONREC.2019.05.019>
- 466 Beccarello, M., Di Foggia, G., 2018. Moving towards a circular economy: economic
 467 impacts of higher material recycling targets. *Mater. Today Proc.* 5, 531–543.
 468 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2017.11.115>
- 469 Beccarello, M., Di Foggia, G., 2016. Economic Analysis of EU Strengthened Packaging
 470 Waste Recycling Targets. *J. Adv. Res. Law Econ.* 7, 1930–1941.
 471 [https://doi.org/10.14505/jarle.v7.8\(22\).02](https://doi.org/10.14505/jarle.v7.8(22).02)
- 472 Bel, G., Fageda, X., 2010. Empirical analysis of solid management waste costs: Some
 473 evidence from Galicia, Spain. *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.* 54, 187–193.
 474 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.RESCONREC.2009.07.015>
- 475 Benito-López, B., Moreno-Enguix, M. del R., Solana-Ibañez, J., 2011. Determinants of
 476 efficiency in the provision of municipal street-cleaning and refuse collection
 477 services. *Waste Manag.* 31, 1099–1108.
 478 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.WASMAN.2011.01.019>
- 479 Bohm, R.A., Folz, D.H., Kinnaman, T.C., Podolsky, M.J., 2010. The costs of municipal
 480 waste and recycling programs. *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.* 54, 864–871.
 481 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2010.01.005>
- 482 Buclet, N., Godard, O., 2001. The evolution of municipal waste management in Europe:
 483 how different are national regimes? *J. Environ. Policy Plan.* 3, 303–317.
 484 <https://doi.org/10.1002/jepp.91>
- 485 Callan, S.J., Thomas, J.M., 2001. Economies of scale and scope: A cost analysis of
 486 municipal solid waste services. *Land Econ.* 77, 548–560.
 487 <https://doi.org/10.2307/3146940>
- 488 Chifari, R., Lo Piano, S., Matsumoto, S., Tasaki, T., 2017. Does recyclable separation
 489 reduce the cost of municipal waste management in Japan? *Waste Manag.* 60, 32–
 490 41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.WASMAN.2017.01.015>
- 491 Chu, Z., Wang, W., Zhou, A., Huang, W.-C., 2019. Charging for municipal solid waste
 492 disposal in Beijing. *Waste Manag.* 94, 85–94.
 493 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.WASMAN.2019.05.051>
- 494 D’Onza, G., Greco, G., Allegrini, M., 2016. Full cost accounting in the analysis of
 495 separated waste collection efficiency: A methodological proposal. *J. Environ.*
 496 *Manage.* 167, 59–65. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JENVMAN.2015.09.002>

- 497 Da Cruz, N.F., Simões, P., Marques, R.C., 2014. Costs and benefits of packaging waste
498 recycling systems. *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.* 85, 1–4.
499 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2014.01.006>
- 500 De Jaeger, S., Eyckmans, J., Rogge, N., Van Puyenbroeck, T., 2011. Wasteful waste-
501 reducing policies? The impact of waste reduction policy instruments on collection
502 and processing costs of municipal solid waste. *Waste Manag.* 31, 1429–1440.
503 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.WASMAN.2011.02.021>
- 504 De Jaeger, S., Rogge, N., 2013. Waste pricing policies and cost-efficiency in municipal
505 waste services: The case of Flanders. *Waste Manag. Res.* 31, 751–758.
506 <https://doi.org/10.1177/0734242X13484189>
- 507 Debnath, S., Bose, S.K., 2014. Exploring full cost accounting approach to evaluate cost
508 of MSW services in India. *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.* 83, 87–95.
509 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.RESCONREC.2013.12.007>
- 510 Di Foggia, G., Beccarello, M., 2020. The impact of a gain-sharing cost-reflective tariff
511 on waste management cost under incentive regulation: The Italian case. *J.*
512 *Environ. Manage.* 265, 110526. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2020.110526>
- 513 Di Foggia, G., Beccarello, M., 2018. Improving efficiency in the MSW collection and
514 disposal service combining price cap and yardstick regulation: The Italian case.
515 *Waste Manag.* 79, 223–231. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2018.07.040>
- 516 Dijkgraaf, E., Gradus, R., 2015. Efficiency Effects of Unit-Based Pricing Systems and
517 Institutional Choices of Waste Collection. *Environ. Resour. Econ.* 61, 641–658.
518 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10640-014-9811-y>
- 519 Fuss, M., Vasconcelos Barros, R.T., Poganietz, W.-R., 2018. Designing a framework for
520 municipal solid waste management towards sustainability in emerging economy
521 countries - An application to a case study in Belo Horizonte (Brazil). *J. Clean.*
522 *Prod.* 178, 655–664. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JCLEPRO.2018.01.051>
- 523 Goddard, H.C., 1995. The benefits and costs of alternative solid waste management
524 policies. *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.* 13, 183–213. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0921-3449\(94\)00021-V](https://doi.org/10.1016/0921-3449(94)00021-V)
- 526 Greco, G., Allegrini, M., Del Lungo, C., Gori Savellini, P., Gabellini, L., 2015. Drivers of
527 solid waste collection costs. Empirical evidence from Italy. *J. Clean. Prod.* 106,
528 364–371. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2014.07.011>
- 529 Greco, G., Cenciarelli, V.G., Allegrini, M., 2018. Tourism's impacts on the costs of
530 municipal solid waste collection: Evidence from Italy. *J. Clean. Prod.* 177, 62–68.
531 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JCLEPRO.2017.12.179>
- 532 Guerrini, A., Carvalho, P., Romano, G., Cunha Marques, R., Leardini, C., 2017.
533 Assessing efficiency drivers in municipal solid waste collection services through a
534 non-parametric method. *J. Clean. Prod.* 147, 431–441.
535 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.01.079>
- 536 Gullì, L., Zazzi, M., 2011. Renewal strategies for the environmental conversion of crafts
537 districts in Italy. *Procedia Eng.* 21, 771–779.
538 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeng.2011.11.2077>
- 539 Hoornweg, D., Bhada-Tata, P., 2012. What a waste. A Global Review of Solid Waste

540 Management (No. 15), Urban Development knowledge. Washington.

541 Jacobsen, R., Buysse, J., Gellynck, X., 2013. Cost comparison between private and
542 public collection of residual household waste: Multiple case studies in the Flemish
543 region of Belgium. *Waste Manag.* 33, 3–11.
544 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2012.08.015>

545 Johnstone, N., Labonne, J., 2004. Generation of Household Solid Waste in OECD
546 Countries: An Empirical Analysis Using Macroeconomic Data. *Land Econ.* 80,
547 529–528. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3655808>

548 Kinnaman, T.C., 2009. The economics of municipal solid waste management. *Waste*
549 *Manag.* 29, 2615–2617. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2009.06.031>

550 Lavee, D., 2007. Is Municipal Solid Waste Recycling Economically Efficient? *Environ.*
551 *Manage.* 40, 926–943. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00267-007-9000-7>

552 Lavee, D., Khatib, M., 2010. Benchmarking in municipal solid waste recycling. *Waste*
553 *Manag.* 30, 2204–2208. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.WASMAN.2010.03.032>

554 Lavee, D., Nardiya, S., 2013. A cost evaluation method for transferring municipalities
555 to solid waste source-separated system. *Waste Manag.* 33, 1064–1072.
556 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.WASMAN.2013.01.026>

557 Liu, Y., Ge, Y., Xia, B., Cui, C., Jiang, X., Skitmore, M., 2019. Enhancing public
558 acceptance towards waste-to-energy incineration projects: Lessons learned from
559 a case study in China. *Sustain. Cities Soc.* 48, 101582.
560 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SCS.2019.101582>

561 Lombrano, A., 2009. Cost efficiency in the management of solid urban waste. *Resour.*
562 *Conserv. Recycl.* 53, 601–611.
563 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.RESCONREC.2009.04.017>

564 Makarichi, L., Jutidamrongphan, W., Techato, K., 2018. The evolution of waste-to-
565 energy incineration: A review. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 91, 812–821.
566 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.RSER.2018.04.088>

567 Malinauskaite, J., Jouhara, H., Czajczyńska, D., Stanchev, P., Katsou, E., Rostkowski,
568 P., Thorne, R.J., Colón, J., Ponsá, S., Al-Mansour, F., Anguilano, L., Krzyżyńska,
569 R., López, I.C., Vlasopoulos, A., Spencer, N., 2017. Municipal solid waste
570 management and waste-to-energy in the context of a circular economy and energy
571 recycling in Europe. *Energy* 141, 2013–2044.
572 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENERGY.2017.11.128>

573 Mani, S., Singh, S., 2016. Sustainable Municipal Solid Waste Management in India: A
574 Policy Agenda. *Procedia Environ. Sci.* 35, 150–157.
575 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.PROENV.2016.07.064>

576 Mazzanti, M., Montini, A., Zoboli, R., 2008. Municipal Waste Generation and
577 Socioeconomic Drivers. Evidence From Comparing Northern and Southern Italy.
578 *J. Environ. Dev.* 17, 51–69. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1070496507312575>

579 Pan, S.-Y., Du, M.A., Huang, I.-T., Liu, I.-H., Chang, E.-E., Chiang, P.-C., 2015.
580 Strategies on implementation of waste-to-energy (WTE) supply chain for circular
581 economy system: a review. *J. Clean. Prod.* 108, 409–421.
582 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JCLEPRO.2015.06.124>

- 583 Passarini, F., Vassura, I., Monti, F., Morselli, L., Villani, B., 2011. Indicators of waste
584 management efficiency related to different territorial conditions. *Waste Manag.*
585 31, 785–792. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2010.11.021>
- 586 Pérez-López, G., Prior, D., Zafra-Gómez, J.L., Plata-Díaz, A.M., 2016. Cost efficiency
587 in municipal solid waste service delivery. *Alternative management forms in*
588 *relation to local population size. Eur. J. Oper. Res.* 255, 583–592.
589 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2016.05.034>
- 590 Plata-Díaz, A.M., Zafra-Gómez, J.L., Pérez-López, G., López-Hernández, A.M., 2014.
591 *Alternative management structures for municipal waste collection services: The*
592 *influence of economic and political factors. Waste Manag.* 34, 1967–1976.
593 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2014.07.003>
- 594 Sarra, A., Mazzocchitti, M., Rapposelli, A., 2017. Evaluating joint environmental and
595 cost performance in municipal waste management systems through data
596 envelopment analysis: Scale effects and policy implications. *Ecol. Indic.* 73.
597 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2016.10.035>
- 598 Scharff, H., 2014. Landfill reduction experience in The Netherlands. *Waste Manag.* 34,
599 2218–2224. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.WASMAN.2014.05.019>
- 600 Simões, P., Cruz, N.F., Marques, R.C., 2012. The performance of private partners in the
601 waste sector. *J. Clean. Prod.* 29–30, 214–221.
602 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2012.01.027>
- 603 Simões, P., Marques, R.C., 2012a. Influence of regulation on the productivity of waste
604 utilities. What can we learn with the Portuguese experience? *Waste Manag.* 32,
605 1266–1275. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.WASMAN.2012.02.004>
- 606 Simões, P., Marques, R.C., 2012b. On the economic performance of the waste sector. A
607 literature review. *J. Environ. Manage.* 106, 40–47.
608 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2012.04.005>
- 609 Swart, J., Groot, L., 2015. Waste management alternatives: (Dis)economies of scale in
610 recovery and decoupling. *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.* 94, 43–55.
611 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.RESCONREC.2014.11.005>
- 612 Tisserant, A., Pauliuk, S., Merciai, S., Schmidt, J., Fry, J., Wood, R., Tukker, A., 2017.
613 *Solid Waste and the Circular Economy: A Global Analysis of Waste Treatment and*
614 *Waste Footprints. J. Ind. Ecol.* 21, 628–640. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.12562>
- 615 Tsilemou, K., Panagiotakopoulos, D., 2006. Approximate cost functions for solid waste
616 treatment facilities. *Waste Manag. Res.* 24, 310–322.
617 <https://doi.org/10.1177/0734242X06066343>
- 618 UNEP, 2012. *Sustainable, Resource Efficient Cities - Making It Happen.* United
619 Nations Environment.
- 620 World Bank, 2018. *Municipal solid waste management. A roadmap for reform for*
621 *policy makers.*
- 622 Zeller, V., Towa, E., Degrez, M., Achten, W.M.J., 2019. Urban waste flows and their
623 potential for a circular economy model at city-region level. *Waste Manag.* 83, 83–
624 94. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.WASMAN.2018.10.034>

626 Annex 1. correlation matrix of all the variables used in the models inherent to unsorted waste

	axr	coast	alt	perso	kg	rev	density	scale	wte	land	mbt
axr	1,000	-0,042	0,141	-0,071	0,066	0,175	-0,340	-0,170	-0,057	0,063	-0,040
coast	-0,042	1,000	-0,362	-0,193	0,214	-0,002	0,210	0,278	-0,227	0,219	0,260
alt	0,141	-0,362	1,000	-0,228	-0,210	0,434	-0,507	-0,354	0,007	0,178	0,097
perso	-0,071	-0,193	-0,228	1,000	-0,085	-0,213	0,266	0,018	0,150	-0,447	-0,466
kg	0,066	0,214	-0,210	-0,085	1,000	-0,414	0,252	0,185	0,110	-0,181	-0,243
rev	0,225	0,105	0,371	-0,276	0,050	1,000	-0,604	-0,292	-0,237	0,295	0,338
den	-0,365	0,171	-0,479	0,292	0,047	-0,564	1,000	0,454	0,189	-0,263	-0,162
scale	-0,170	0,278	-0,354	0,018	0,185	-0,227	0,429	1,000	-0,167	0,110	0,163
wte	-0,057	-0,227	0,007	0,150	0,110	-0,204	0,172	-0,167	1,000	-0,427	-0,377
land	0,063	0,219	0,178	-0,447	-0,181	0,232	-0,233	0,110	-0,427	1,000	0,675
mbt	-0,040	0,260	0,097	-0,466	-0,243	0,248	-0,115	0,163	-0,377	0,675	1,000

627

628 Annex 2. correlation matrix of all the variables used in the models inherent to sorted waste

	axr	coast	alt	perso	kg	rev	density	scale	plastic	paper	metal	glass	wet	mbt	Integ	Adig	compo
axr	1,000	-0,042	0,117	-0,074	0,052	0,153	-0,346	-0,161	0,059	0,046	0,084	0,101	-0,081	-0,017	0,036	-0,047	-0,011
coast	-0,042	1,000	-0,370	-0,221	0,239	0,016	0,201	0,280	-0,062	0,069	-0,084	-0,007	0,052	0,273	-0,187	-0,150	-0,074
alt	0,117	-0,370	1,000	-0,168	-0,219	0,401	-0,460	-0,338	0,143	0,111	0,156	0,288	-0,338	0,089	-0,210	-0,167	-0,012
perso	-0,074	-0,221	-0,168	1,000	-0,179	-0,130	0,174	-0,045	-0,174	-0,371	-0,014	-0,352	0,459	-0,404	0,350	0,177	0,085
kg	0,052	0,239	-0,219	-0,179	1,000	-0,413	0,257	0,209	-0,129	0,092	0,057	-0,152	-0,096	-0,211	0,026	0,154	0,044
rev	0,194	0,142	0,326	-0,235	0,065	1,000	-0,566	-0,249	0,162	0,012	0,073	0,320	-0,064	0,340	-0,229	-0,281	-0,206
den	-0,368	0,156	-0,429	0,218	0,051	-0,517	1,000	0,435	-0,218	-0,050	-0,184	-0,403	0,252	-0,150	0,035	0,120	0,026
scale	-0,161	0,280	-0,338	-0,045	0,209	-0,164	0,405	1,000	-0,184	0,150	-0,151	-0,348	0,251	0,194	-0,088	0,057	-0,011
plastic	0,059	-0,062	0,143	-0,174	-0,129	0,111	-0,197	-0,184	1,000	0,083	0,009	-0,027	-0,311	0,104	-0,056	-0,115	-0,202
paper	0,046	0,069	0,111	-0,371	0,092	0,061	-0,071	0,150	0,083	1,000	-0,052	0,077	-0,470	0,154	-0,145	-0,109	0,077
metal	0,084	-0,084	0,156	-0,014	0,057	0,110	-0,202	-0,151	0,009	-0,052	1,000	0,069	-0,308	-0,219	0,202	0,089	-0,051
glass	0,101	-0,007	0,288	-0,352	-0,152	0,272	-0,383	-0,348	-0,027	0,077	0,069	1,000	-0,478	0,112	-0,074	-0,088	-0,005
wet	-0,081	0,052	-0,338	0,459	-0,096	-0,120	0,282	0,251	-0,311	-0,470	-0,308	-0,478	1,000	0,102	0,021	0,006	-0,042

mbt	-0,017	0,273	0,089	-0,404	-0,211	0,263	-0,110	0,194	0,104	0,154	-0,219	0,112	0,102	1,000	-0,488	-0,335	-0,072
integ	0,036	-0,187	-0,210	0,350	0,026	-0,237	0,030	-0,088	-0,056	-0,145	0,202	-0,074	0,021	-0,488	1,000	0,207	-0,007
adig	-0,047	-0,150	-0,167	0,177	0,154	-0,228	0,092	0,057	-0,115	-0,109	0,089	-0,088	0,006	-0,335	0,207	1,000	0,156
compo	-0,011	-0,074	-0,012	0,085	0,044	-0,203	0,017	-0,011	-0,202	0,077	-0,051	-0,005	-0,042	-0,072	-0,007	0,156	1,000

629

630

631 Annex 3. VIFs for per ton models as in table 2 and table 3

	swc	ctc	tdc	UNMC	MC	msc	trc	SOMC	MC
Table 2									
den	2.38	2.36	2.32	2.35	2.35				
mbt	2.25	2.32	2.29	2.33	2.33				
land	2.11	2.16	2.17	2.17	2.17				
rev	2.03	2.1	2.1	2.11	2.1				
alt	1.77	1.69	1.67	1.69	1.7				
perso	1.58	1.59	1.58	1.59	1.58				
coast	1.53	1.5	1.5	1.49	1.53				
scale	1.5	1.5	1.49	1.49	1.5				
kg	1.47	1.46	1.48	1.47	1.48				
wte	1.33	1.38	1.4	1.37	1.37				
axr	1.16	1.18	1.17	1.18	1.18				
Mean VIF	1.74	1.75	1.74	1.75	1.75				
Table 3									
bio						3.23	3.14	3.29	3.28
den						2.23	2.24	2.24	2.24
rev						2.17	2.19	2.16	2.16
mbt						2.14	2.15	2.15	2.14
glass						2.07	1.97	2.07	2.08
perso						2.07	1.97	2.06	2.06
alt						1.86	1.86	1.85	1.86
paper						1.68	1.68	1.68	1.69
scale						1.63	1.61	1.64	1.65
kg						1.57	1.6	1.57	1.58
coast						1.54	1.56	1.54	1.57
integ						1.54	1.54	1.53	1.54
plastic						1.51	1.53	1.5	1.5
metal						1.35	1.51	1.35	1.35
adig						1.27	1.34	1.27	1.25
axr						1.18	1.21	1.18	1.18
compo						1.17	1.17	1.17	1.17
Mean VIF						1.78	1.78	1.78	1.78

632

633 Annex 4. VIFs for per capita models as in table 4 and table 5

	swc	ctc	tdc	UNMC	MC	msc	trc	SOMC	MC
f	a. Table 4								
mbt	2.28	2.31	2.3	2.32	2.33				
den	2.18	2.22	2.17	2.21	2.21				
land	2.14	2.16	2.17	2.16	2.17				
rev	1.74	1.75	1.73	1.75	1.75				
alt	1.73	1.69	1.67	1.69	1.7				
perso	1.59	1.59	1.59	1.58	1.58				
coast	1.52	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.53				
scale	1.48	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5				

kg	1.37	1.38	1.4	1.37	1.37
wte	1.35	1.35	1.35	1.36	1.36
axr	1.18	1.18	1.17	1.18	1.18
Mean VIF	1.69	1.69	1.68	1.69	1.7

b. Table 5

bio	3.23	3.1	3.3	3.28
mbt	2.15	2.23	2.15	2.14
den	2.1	2.04	2.1	2.09
perso	2.08	1.94	2.07	2.08
glass	2.06	1.93	2.06	2.06
alt	1.85	1.85	1.85	1.86
rev	1.81	1.81	1.8	1.8
paper	1.68	1.67	1.69	1.69
scale	1.64	1.62	1.64	1.65
coast	1.54	1.6	1.55	1.58
kg	1.54	1.54	1.54	1.54
integ	1.54	1.53	1.53	1.53
plastic	1.51	1.51	1.5	1.5
metal	1.36	1.5	1.35	1.35
adig	1.27	1.35	1.26	1.25
axr	1.18	1.21	1.18	1.18
compo	1.17	1.16	1.17	1.17
Mean VIF	1.75	1.74	1.75	1.75

634

635